

Carbon Nanotube Buoyancy Space Elevator

Carbon Nanotube buoyancy bubble at different stage of the atmosphere is to be placed and elevator ropes to be dropped accordingly. Rest of the design is classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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The physical measurement system will follow during these development and assessment. We might also derive information regarding their potential **design under** mechanical stress and physical space constraints within their...

